

Applying Sentinel-2 Deep Resolution 3.0 (S2DR3) for supervised classification of coastal environments

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Abstract

The study evaluates the impact of improved spatial resolution on the supervised classification of coastal environments using the Random Forest algorithm. Two versions of a Sentinel-2 image were compared: one with an original spatial resolution of 10 meters and the other transformed to 1 meter using the Sentinel-2 Deep Resolution 3.0 (S2DR3) super-resolution algorithm, based on artificial intelligence techniques.

The classification was performed using five thematic classes: water bodies, wetlands, urban areas, exposed soil, and vegetation. Training samples were collected using Google Earth Pro, and the performance metrics evaluated included confusion matrix, accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score.

The results demonstrated that the 1-meter resolution image provided higher accuracy (94%) and less confusion between classes, especially for small objects such as buildings and roads. The original image (10 m) achieved 89% accuracy and showed greater spectral overlap between classes, such as exposed soil and urban areas. However, at both resolutions, there was confusion between these classes, attributed to the spectral similarity of the targets.

We conclude that improving spatial resolution via S2DR3 enhances the quality of supervised classification, but does not completely eliminate errors caused by spectral similarity. The use of spectral indices, such as NDVI, and an increased number of samples can complement this approach, improving the results.

1 Introduction

With the advancement of Remote Sensing (RS), the availability of orbital data has gained momentum, becoming an important tool for monitoring, planning and managing diverse environments, whether urban, rural, marine, natural or deforested [9]. However, even with technological advances in RS, limitations in spatial, spectral and temporal resolution still persist compromising information extraction, such as for supervised image classification, where precise target identification is required.

Supervised classification of satellite images is a processing technique used to automatically identify different land cover types, based on previously labeled samples for training classifier algorithms [12, 15]. One such algorithm is the decision tree-based machine learning model, Random Forest [4], which presents high accuracy, low overfitting, and the ability to handle multispectral data [2]. Furthermore, Random Forest has a good ability to correctly classify targets with similar spectral signatures and also provides important measures to identify which bands or indices best contribute to classification [14].

Even with improved classifier performance, good spatial resolution is essential for good classification. Therefore, Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques are gaining prominence in improving (reducing) pixel size. The Single Image Super-Resolution (SISR) technique is one example of this method developed as the Sentinel-2 Deep Resolution 3.0 (S2DR3) algorithm, which converts 60 meters, 20 meters and 10 meters

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Sentinel images to approximately 1 meter pixels resolution, using total configuration architecture [1], that is, a mathematical operation called convolution is applied to the input images, functioning as a filter, extracting patterns such as edges, textures, shapes and more complex structures from the image. These filters have weights that are calculated throughout the image, generating a feature map, which will be used to detect the details of the image, helping to improve the pixel size [6].

Therefore, the objective of this study was to compare the use of the Random Forest classifier for coastal targets on two different Sentinel-2 images: a 10 meters original image and the same image with resolution enhanced to 1 meter by S2DR3. We sought to identify potential advantages and disadvantages for classification based on improved spatial resolution.

2 Methodology

To compare the classifications in images transformed by the SISR method, we acquired on April 26, 2025, without cloud cover and processed at level 2A, an image from the Sentinel-2 satellite, with an area of 16 km², located in Salinas da Margarida, municipality in the state of Bahia (Latitude 12.88° S, Longitude 38.75° W), a region with diversity of land use and land cover.

The methodology can be divided into two parts: 1) Image enhancement using the S2DR3 method and 2) Application of Random Forest for the classification of images with 10 meters and 1 meter spatial resolution.

1) Bands 4 (red, 10 m), 8 (near infrared - NIR, 20 m) and 12 (shortwave infrared - SWIR, 20 m) were combined in the false color composite, aiding in the identification of vegetation, exposed soil and built-up areas. These bands were enhanced by the S2DR3 AI, increasing from 10/20 m spatial resolution to 1 m.

2) With the image transformed to 1 meter, we applied the Random Forest method as a classifier. Five classes were defined: water body, flooded area, built-up areas, exposed soil and vegetation. For each class, an average of 10 samples were collected, randomly collected, within the Sentinel-2 image. Images provided by Google Earth Pro were also used as ground truth. The classification was applied in a Python environment, using the scikit-learn library [7], using 100 decision trees ($n_estimator = 100$). Finally, evaluation metrics were generated, such as the confusion matrix, precision, recall, F1-score and accuracy.

3 Results and Discussion

The results presented by the Random Forest classification visually showed notable differences as shown in the figure 1. It is possible to note that built-up areas were better classified in the 1m image (Figure 1.A), in which better spatial resolutions improve the detection of smaller targets, such as houses and roads (e.g., [3, 12]). The boundary of water bodies also had better classification in the AI-transformed image (1 m) (Figure 1.C), once again, images with finer spatial resolution, that is, with smaller pixel size, achieve a greater level of detail for smaller objects and with complex geometries [11, 13].

In addition to the visual analysis, statistical tests were carried out to assess the performance of the classifier in images with different resolutions. For statistical analysis, confusion matrices (Figure 2) and statistical metrics, accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score were generated [5]. In a confusion matrix, it is important to understand that the rows represent the actual classes, the columns represent the predicted classes, the diagonal values are the correct classifications, and the off-diagonal values are the classification errors. Thus, the matrix for the 10 meters image showed that Random Forest performed well for the flooded area, exposed soil, and vegetation classes. However, for the water body and built-up area classes, the model did not perform so well, particularly for the built-up area, where it presented a 50% classification error, confusing exposed soil with built-up (Figure 2, 10-meter image). These errors may occur due to the spectral similarity of the targets and the sample similarity of the targets and the sample size may have been insufficient for model training [11, 12].

Regarding the confusion matrix of the image improved by S2DR3 (Figure 2, 1m image), the built-up area was the only one with performance lower than 100%, presenting confusion with the exposed soil, the same happening with the 10 m image. This type of error is common for areas with spectral similarity, such as rooftops and highways, and can be confused with areas of soil without vegetation cover [10, 11].

Figure 1. Random Forest classification for original Sentinel-2 image (10 m resolution spatial) on the left and for the S2DR3 version Sentinel-2 image (1 m resolution spatial) on the right. The areas A, B and C display zoomed-in views of different targets for resolution comparison.

With 94% accuracy, Random Forest performed well in classifying the 1-meter image, but missed 100% between the built-up area and exposed soil classes. The exposed soil class had a recall of 0.50, indicating that only half of the pixels correctly belonging to this class were recognized by the model. Despite this, its precision was 1.00, meaning that all pixels classified as exposed soil were in fact correct. The built-up areas presented the opposite scenario, a recall of 1.00, no built-up areas examples were missed, but a precision of 0.67, evidencing the presence of false positives, one exposed soil pixel was incorrectly classified as urban.

Analysis of the image with a 10 meters spatial resolution resulted in an overall accuracy of 89%. The results demonstrate satisfactory performance in classifying thematic classes, but lower than that observed with high-resolution images, such as 1 meter. This difference is related to the low ability to distinguish between spectrally similar targets, common in sensors with lower spatial resolution [8, 13]. The body water had a precision of 1 and recall of 0.80, demonstrating that some water pixels were misclassified as flooded areas. The flooded area class had perfect recall (1.00) and a precision of 0.86, with confusion arising from the "water" class. The same occurs with exposed soil with low recall (0.50), which may be related to the spectral similarity between sidewalks, rooftops, and dry soil, and the built-up areas with errors originating from the exposed soil.

Figure 2. Confusion matrices for Random Forest classification.

4 Conclusion

The image with the highest resolution (1 m pixel size) performed better in Random Forest, with 94% accuracy, compared to 89% for the image with the lowest resolution (10 m), which showed greater confusion between its classes, with the water body class having pixels confused with the flooded area class and the built-up area class confused with exposed soil.

While the original image had two classes with classification confusion, the highest resolution image confused only one class, the built-up area with exposed soil. These two classes have very similar spectral signatures, a fact that spatial resolution transformation alone cannot differentiate. The use of spectral indices (e.g., NDVI) can help improve this classification by distinguishing similar spectral signatures [10]. Furthermore, the greater the number of samples, the better for classifier training [2].

In the presented study, the difference between the classifications of the two images is different, with a gain in quality in the image transformed by S2DR3. The random forest classifier performed well, achieving almost 100% accuracy when applied to an image with a smaller pixel size, resulting in less confusion between classes and better classification accuracy.

A suggestion for future work is to use AI to classify urban areas or agricultural areas with different crops, where the level of object detail is greater and spectral similarities also increase classification difficulty.

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